

Urachal cancer: a rare and aggressive malignancy - clinical case report and therapeutic management

Kristiyan Dimitrov^{1,2}

1 Clinic of Urology, UMHAT "Alexandrovska", Sofia, Bulgaria

2 Department of Urology, Medical University, Sofia, Bulgaria

Corresponding author: Kristiyan Dimitrov (dr.kr.dimitrov@abv.bg)

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Abstract

Urachal carcinoma is a rare and aggressive tumor arising from the embryonic remnant connecting the bladder dome to the umbilicus. It accounts for less than 1% of bladder cancers and typically affects patients aged 52 to 59 years. Surgical resection with negative margins is the mainstay of treatment for localized disease, often involving urachal excision, partial or radical cystectomy, and lymphadenectomy. Chemotherapy has limited established efficacy but may be used in advanced cases. Five-year overall survival is around 50%, with poorer outcomes in metastatic disease. This report describes a 61-year-old patient presenting with hematuria, diagnosed with urachal adenocarcinoma through cystoscopy and biopsy. The patient underwent radical surgery with complete tumor removal followed by regular PET scan follow-up. This case highlights the importance of early detection and definitive surgical management of this rare malignancy.

Keywords

urachal carcinoma, partial cystectomy, urachus excision

Introduction

The urachus is a vestigial structure arising from the embryonic allantois, establishing a conduit between the fetal bladder and the umbilicus. Normally, this channel involutes during gestation and forms the median umbilical ligament, with complete luminal obliteration by the third trimester. Yet, incomplete regression occurs in a substantial minority of adults, with estimates around 32%, leaving a potential substrate for a spectrum of benign and malignant conditions that can emerge over a patient's lifetime (Bruins et al. 2021). It is within this developmental context that urachal pathology, though

uncommon, can be biologically distinct from conventional bladder diseases.

Urachal carcinoma is an exceptionally rare and aggressive malignancy, accounting for less than 1% of all bladder cancers. Its clinical and anatomic predilections reflect its embryologic origin, with tumors most commonly arising in the anterior bladder wall or at the bladder dome. Histologically, urachal carcinomas are overwhelmingly adenocarcinomas, comprising more than 90% of cases, and are frequently characterized as enteric-type lesions that may harbor features of intestinal metaplasia within urachal epithelium. The pathogenesis is thought to involve metaplastic transformation and subsequent malignant evolution

of urachal mucosa, sometimes with mucin production contributing to the tumor's biology. The insidious onset of disease commonly permits local invasion or distant spread before diagnosis, which translates into a generally unfavorable prognosis relative to other urothelial tumors (Quan et al. 2017; Bruins et al. 2021; Yu et al. 2021).

Because of its rarity, urachal carcinoma lacks universally accepted diagnostic criteria, staging schemes, and consensus on the optimal management strategy. Diagnostic workup typically integrates detailed imaging with histopathologic confirmation. Cross-sectional imaging—computed tomography (CT) or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)—often reveals a midline, anterior bladder dome mass with involvement of the urachus and potential calcifications; these radiographic features can aid differentiation from primary bladder tumors, but histologic confirmation remains essential. Cystoscopic evaluation may localize the tumor to the bladder dome, and transurethral biopsy or resection can provide diagnostic tissue, though sampling can be challenging. Immunohistochemical profiling frequently demonstrates markers consistent with enteric differentiation, including CDX2 positivity, supporting the diagnosis of urachal adenocarcinoma. Staging systems proposed for urachal cancer include historical frameworks such as the Sheldon and Mayo Clinic schemes, as well as contemporary TNM-based approaches, reflecting the disease's unique anatomic and biological behavior.

Management is principally surgical when the disease is localized and resectable. The cornerstone of curative-intent treatment is en bloc excision of the urachus, umbilicus, and the involved portion of the bladder (often via partial cystectomy) with wide negative margins. Achieving negative margins is particularly critical in partial cystectomy, as positive margins correlate with poorer overall and cancer-specific survival. Perioperative chemotherapy has a limited and evolving role; neoadjuvant therapy may be considered in unresectable cases to downstage disease and enable curative surgery in a subset of patients. Platinum-based chemotherapy regimens tend to achieve better disease control, although definitive survival advantages over other regimens (e.g., paclitaxel- or fluorouracil-based protocols) have not been consistently demonstrated. Given the rarity of the disease, treatment is typically individualized within multidisciplinary tumor boards.

This report describes the clinical and therapeutic management of a 61-year-old patient presenting with macroscopic hematuria. Cystoscopy and transurethral resection of a suspicious mass arising in the bladder dome yielded histologic confirmation of urachal adenocarcinoma, and the patient subsequently underwent radical surgical management with careful postoperative follow-up, including serial surveillance with positron emission tomography (PET) imaging. This case adds to the body of clinical experience guiding multidisciplinary decision-making in urachal cancer, highlighting the importance of early, definitive surgical resection with negative margins, comprehensive staging, and structured imaging-based follow-up to optimize outcomes.

Case presentation

It concerns a 61-year-old man with complaints of intermittent painless macroscopic hematuria for several weeks. He was previously healthy with no known diseases. Physical examination showed no obvious abnormalities. Urinalysis was positive for red blood cells, $874 \times 10^6/L$, and white blood cells, $6 \times 10^6/L$. Ultrasound examination revealed a solid heteroechoic mass with calcifications, which could be considered pathognomonic according to Monteiro V(34), in the midline of the lower abdomen, invading the anteroinferior wall of the bladder with ill-defined irregularly shaped protrusions outside the bladder (Fig. 1) Internal echogenicity is heterogeneous and uneven calcifications and a small amount of punctate and short-line blood flow are observed in the tumor. No enlarged lymph nodes were noted in the abdominal cavity or retroperitoneum.

Figure 1. Ultrasound image of the calcified heteroechoic mass.

Taking into account the ultrasound, the next step we did was cystoscopy. A suspicious formation with a broad base and infiltrative nature was found on the cupula of the bladder. Therefore, a decision was made to perform a transurethral resection of the latter, as radicality could not be achieved (Meeks 2013). Material was taken for histological examination.

Histopathological verification

The latter concluded that it was tumor tissue composed of highly atypical tumor cells, forming papillary structures and small glands, with the presence of numerous psammomatous bodies (Fig. 2). The tumor involved the bladder transmurally, and in one of the fragments reached the perivesical fatty tissue, with single tumor emboli. Presence of perineural invasion.

Immunohistochemical analysis showed the following results: CDX2 exhibited a positive nuclear expression. Beta-catenin showed a positive membrane reaction, with no nuclear staining. GATA3 was negative. CK7 displayed positive staining in a small proportion of tumor cells.

Urachal adenocarcinoma, enteric type, demonstrated transmural infiltration of the bladder with initial involvement of the paravesical fat tissue. Histopathological evaluation revealed the presence of lymphovascular and perineural invasion, consistent with an aggressive tumor behavior and extended local spread typically observed in this subtype.

Figure 2. Histopathological slide displaying highly atypical tumor cells forming papillary and glandular structures with numerous psammoma bodies.

Imaging of the abdomen was ordered to further assess the mass. Contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CT) of the abdomen revealed a hyperdense conical mass with intramural infiltration, involving an arcuate area of the anterior bladder wall measuring 34 mm/35 mm (Fig. 3A), enhancing on contrast with fine paravesical striated changes in the fatty tissue. There was no significant lymphadenomegaly.

Transverse section after transurethral resection reveals a crater-like defect in the anterior bladder wall at the cupula area, which is filled with contrast material during the urographic phase. Additionally, uneven thickening of the bladder wall is observed (Fig. 3B). A sagittal section confirms these findings, demonstrating the same features described above.

Fig. 4 displays 3D modeling of the patient's urinary system, illustrating the precise localization of the lesion along the bladder wall. The model also shows no obstruction in the excretion of contrast material from the kidneys bilaterally, indicating preserved renal outflow.

A decision was made for open surgery. The bladder was carefully dissected from the adjacent structures. On its anterior wall in the area of the bladder dome, the urachus was found, covered by a tumor formation with rough borders and increased density. A partial resection of the bladder in the area of the bladder dome was performed with excision of the adjacent peritoneum and urachus in an en bloc preparation together with the umbilical structures. Pathology confirmed the diagnosis of urachal adenocarcinoma of enteric type with infiltration of the full thickness of the muscle layer into the perivesical fatty tissue, without involvement of the serosa. Furthermore, without involvement of the resection lines. Therefore, no adjuvant chemotherapy was administered.

Following histological confirmation of complete tumor resection with negative margins, the case was reviewed by an oncology committee. It was recommended to perform a staging positron emission tomography (PET) scan 45 days postoperatively to assess for residual disease or metastasis.

A

B

Figure 3. **A.** Contrast-enhanced transverse CT showing a hyperdense mass with intramural infiltration of the anterior bladder wall measuring 34 × 35 mm; **B.** Sagittal section of urographic phase CT revealing thickening of the bladder wall consistent with tumor infiltration.

Figure 4. 3D modeling of the patient's urinary system.

A transverse PET-CT image (Fig. 5A) demonstrated no significantly increased metabolic activity suggestive of tumor dissemination. The radiopharmaceutical used was ^{18}F -FDG. In conditions of an optimally filled bladder and against the background of physiological urinary accumulation of radiopharmaceutical, the anterior wall of the bladder appears unevenly thickened, without demarcating focal hypermetabolic lesions. Data are established for increased fixation of the radiopharmaceutical medially along the course of the surgical approach, most pronounced in the muscles of the anterior abdominal wall, with a maximum SUV of up to 4.8. Additionally, behind the anterior abdominal wall, ventral and cranial to the bladder, striated fibrous seals with slightly increased fixation of the radiopharmaceutical are observed, more pronounced to the left of the midline, with a maximum SUV of up to 3.6, indistinguishable from reactive/postoperative. No foci of pathological glucose metabolism were detected in the remaining abdominal organs, and there was no evidence of metabolically active pathological changes in the lymph nodes in the abdomen and pelvis, as well as the corresponding bone structures.

Given the histologically proven radical surgical treatment and the missing data from PET-CT for local and distant lymphogenous and/or hematogenous metastases, the oncology committee decided on active follow-up. As a consequence, a new staging PET-CT was performed 6 months later (Fig. 5B).

Fig. 6 presents the whole-body PET-CT image in the coronal plane, acquired 115 minutes after intravenous injection of 179 MBq of ^{18}F -FDG combined with a low-dose CT scan.

Discussion

The urachus is an embryonic structure whose function is to establish a connection between the fetal bladder and the allantois during intrauterine fetal development. Through the fourth and fifth months of embryonic life, the urachus gradually atrophies and passes to a rudimentary tubular fibromuscular structure known in adults as the median umbilical ligament. The latter is located between the dome of the bladder and the navel. Autopsy studies suggested that in one-third of adults, the urachus canal partly persists. However, in some rare cases, failure of this process may lead to proliferation of small islets of glandular cells, leading to malignancy. Urachal carcinoma is a rare malignancy accounting for less than 1% (0.35% – 0.70%) of all bladder cancers, with a median age of presentation of 52–59 years, and there is a tendency to affect a younger group of patients than the urothelial bladder cancer (Szarvas et al. 2016). In the largest series to date, the reported 5-year overall survival (OS) was about 50%, and the 5-year cancer-specific survival (CSS) was about 35% (Yu et al. 2021). However, the median survival for locally advanced or metastatic disease is between 12 and 24 months (Patel et al. 2023). Furthermore, the late presentation of symptoms, its tendency towards early local invasion and lymphogenous/hematogenous metastasis are 3 characteristics of urachal cancer that predispose to a poor prognosis (Juhász et al. 2024).

Figure 5. A. Transverse PET-CT; B. PET-CT performed 6 months later.

Figure 6. Whole-body PET-CT image in the coronal plane acquired 115 minutes after intravenous injection of 179 MBq of ^{18}F -FDG, combined with a low-dose CT scan. The image shows radiopharmaceutical accumulation confined to the urinary bladder, with no evidence of local recurrence or distant metastases.

The embryologic origin of the urachus from the allantois underlies the unique histopathologic features of urachal carcinoma. Although the majority of urachal remnants involute, residual epithelial-lined tracts can persist in up to 30% of adults, predisposing them to neoplastic transformation. The most common histological subtype is adenocarcinoma—frequently mucinous in nature—although variants such as signet ring cell carcinoma have also been reported and are associated with a more aggressive clinical course. This rarity, coupled with its atypical location at the bladder dome extending toward the umbilicus, has led to a reliance on case reports and small case series for insights into its biology and optimal management.

Despite the fact that urachus carcinoma has been known and talked about for decades, there are currently no strict and accurate clinical criteria for making a diagnosis. Most scientists and clinicians apply the criteria proposed by Sheldon et al. and Mostofi et al., and revised by Gopalan et al., which include the following characteristics:

- tumor is located in the dome/anterior wall of the bladder,
- tumor growth in the bladder wall,
- absence of urothelial bladder neoplasia,
- absence of known primary adenocarcinoma in another abdominal organ.

The above is also confirmed by the criteria imposed by the MD Anderson Cancer Center (MDACC), consisting of 2 core and 4 supporting criteria (Rajyakodi et al. 2024). The two core criteria are based on the midline location of the tumor on the one hand and on the sharp demarcation between the tumor and the normal surface epithelium on the other (Rajyakodi et al. 2024). Supporting criteria include: intestinal histology; absence of urothelial dysplasia; absence of cystitis cystica; and

absence of primary adenocarcinoma of another origin (Siefker-Radtke 2006; Patel et al. 2023).

Unfortunately, urachal cancer is asymptomatic in its early stages, and patients often present at diagnosis with a higher stage and poor prognosis (Gural et al. 2022). According to some studies, the most common symptom of urachal carcinoma is macroscopic or microscopic hematuria reported in more than 73–75% of patients, followed by abdominal pain and dysuria, mucosuria, as well as recurrent urinary infections (Szarvas et al. 2016). Other less frequent but more specific clinical presentations include umbilical discharge (e.g., blood, urine, and mucus). There are nonspecific symptoms like nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, weight loss, and fever, but they are rare and are more typical of advanced-stage disease. Our patient's presentation aligns with these findings, underscoring the insidious onset of this disease.

Diagnostic evaluation begins with imaging studies. Ultrasound may initially reveal a midline pelvic mass near the bladder dome, but contrast-enhanced computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) are critical for assessing the extent of local invasion, presence of calcifications, and possible distant metastases. Characteristic imaging features include a heterogeneous mass with mixed solid and cystic components and calcific deposits—findings that, while not pathognomonic, heighten the suspicion for a urachal origin (Jaber et al. 2024).

Typically, for urachal carcinoma, the majority of the tumor in 88% of cases is localized outside the lumen of the urinary bladder. Moreover, in over 92% of adenocarcinomas, wall invasion is observed, and distant metastases are found in about 48%, which distinguishes it from urothelial cancer, in which this is much rarer, especially in the early stages. MRI is of great importance in the diagnostic algorithm for making this rare diagnosis, since in T1 sequences the solid component is isointense to the soft tissues and becomes more evident with contrast administration, while focal areas of high intensity in T2 sequences are due to the mucinous component, strongly suggesting adenocarcinoma.

Cystoscopic examination and histopathologic confirmation via biopsy remain the definitive diagnostic steps, with immunohistochemical panels (typically showing positivity for CK20, CDX2, Beta-catenin, and negativity for CK7 and Gata3) providing additional support for a diagnosis of primary urachal adenocarcinoma (Wong-You-Cheong et al. 2006).

Histologically, urachal carcinomas predominantly display glandular differentiation with mucin production. Several staging systems have been proposed, with the Sheldon and Mayo systems (Sheldon et al. 1984) being the most widely referenced. These systems take into account the local extent of disease—from confinement within the urachal remnant to invasion of adjacent organs and distant metastases—which is directly correlated with prognosis. In our case, accurate staging is essential not only for prognostication but also for guiding the therapeutic approach.

The urachal staging system, as defined by Sheldon et al in 1984.

- Stage I – Urachal cancer confined to the urachal mucosa.
- Stage II – Urachal cancer with invasion confined to the urachus itself.
- Stage IIIA – Local urachal cancer extension to the bladder.
- Stage IIIB – Local urachal cancer extension to the abdominal wall.
- Stage IIIC – Local urachal cancer extension to the peritoneum.
- Stage IIID – Local urachal cancer extension to viscera other than bladder.
- Stage IVA – Metastatic urachal cancer to lymph nodes.
- Stage IVB – Metastatic urachal cancer to distant sites.

Surgical resection remains the cornerstone of treatment for localized urachal carcinoma. The standard approach involves partial cystectomy with en bloc excision of the urachal ligament and the umbilicus to achieve negative margins (Jaber et al. 2024). Although some centers advocate radical cystectomy, evidence suggests that partial cystectomy with en bloc urachlectomy to the umbilicus can provide up to 70% complete tumor removal, offering comparable survival outcomes with lower morbidity and invalidation (Juhász et al. 2024). In cases of locally advanced or metastatic disease, the role of adjuvant chemotherapy and radiotherapy is less well defined (Zheng et al. 2021). Current regimens are frequently extrapolated from protocols for colorectal cancer due to the intestinal-type differentiation seen in many urachal tumors. Neoadjuvant chemotherapy may be considered in cases of initially unresectable urachal carcinoma when a favorable therapeutic response could potentially facilitate surgical resection with negative margins (Loizzo et al. 2022).

Recent data from metastatic cohorts, particularly in patients aged ≤ 70 years, suggest that neoadjuvant chemotherapy is associated with reductions in both overall and cancer-specific mortality. Standard regimens typically include 5-fluorouracil in combination with cisplatin or the FOLFOX6 protocol (folinic acid, 5-fluorouracil, and oxaliplatin), with gemcitabine being increasingly incorporated into treatment strategies. A recent study aimed at standardizing chemotherapeutic approaches has demonstrated superior disease control with platinum-based regimens compared to non-platinum-based ones, although no significant differences were observed in progression-free or overall survival between fluorouracil- and paclitaxel-based first-line therapies (Chen et al. 2021).

The combination of systemic chemotherapy with cytoreductive surgery has also shown promising long-term oncologic outcomes. Moreover, in cases where surgical resection is not feasible, chemotherapy should be considered as an appropriate modality for disease control. Nevertheless, the prognosis for advanced disease remains poor, with reported 5-year survival rates ranging widely, from approximately 20% in high-stage disease to near 50% in cases where early-stage tumors are completely resected.

Several prognostic factors have been identified in the literature. Among these, tumor stage at diagnosis, surgical margin status, and the presence of lymph node or distant metastases are consistently associated with outcomes. Negative surgical margins, in particular, have been shown to correlate with improved survival, whereas lymphatic or hematogenous spread markedly worsens the prognosis.

Challenges and future directions

This case highlights the critical importance of early detection and prompt surgical intervention in the management of urachal carcinoma. The patient's initial presentation with hematuria, a common symptom associated with urachal tumors, facilitated the early diagnosis of this rare malignancy. Early-stage identification allowed for complete eradication of the disease through radical surgery, which is the recommended treatment approach for localized urachal carcinoma. This result highlights the need for increased clinical awareness and consideration of urachal carcinoma, especially in younger patients with hematuria, despite it being a relatively rare cause compared to urothelial carcinoma, allowing for timely diagnosis and improved prognostic outcomes.

Despite advances in imaging and surgical techniques, the rarity of urachal carcinoma limits the availability of high-level evidence to guide therapy. Multicenter studies and the establishment of international registries could provide more robust data regarding the optimal management.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

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Author ORCIDs

Kristiyan Dimitrov <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-2805-6252>

Nikolay Dimitrov <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-7133-7628>

Iskren Penkov <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-9607-5617>

Valentin Yotovskii <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1855-0740>

Aleksandar Timev <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-7519-4925>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- Bruins HM, Visser O, Ploeg M, Hulsbergen-van de Kaa CA, Kiemeny LALM, Witjes JA (2012) The clinical epidemiology of urachal carcinoma: results of a large, population based study. *J Urol* 188: 1102–1107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.juro.2012.06.020>
- Chen M, Xue C, Huang RQ, Ni MQ, Li L, Li HF, Yang W, Hu AQ, Zheng ZS, An X, Shi Y (2021) Treatment outcome of different chemotherapy in patients with relapsed or metastatic malignant urachal tumor. *Front Oncol* 11: 739134. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fonc.2021.739134>
- Gural Z, Yücel S, Oskeroğlu S, Ağaoğlu F (2022) Urachal adenocarcinoma: A case report and review of the literature. *J Cancer Res Ther* 18(1): 291–293. https://doi.org/10.4103/jcrt.JCRT_28_20
- Jaber MS, Mojahed S, Rajab BA, Shalodi RY, Abuzaina KNM, Jaber JA (2024) Invasive mucinous urachal adenocarcinoma: A case report of surgical management and insights from the literature. *Int J Surg Case Rep* 125: 110524. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijscr.2024.110524>
- Juhász D, Cszimarik A, Szalontai J, Keszthelyi A, Dér B, Kubik A, Szűcs M, Kenessey I, Ertl IE, Berger W, Englinger B, Shariat SF, Nyirády P, Szarvas T (2024) Precision oncology approach for urachal carcinoma: A clinical case report. *Int J Mol Sci* 25(24): 13315. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms252413315>
- Loizzo D, Pandolfo SD, Crocerossa F, Guruli G, Ferro M, Paul AK, Imbimbo C, Lucarelli G, Ditonno P, Autorino R (2022) Current management of urachal carcinoma: An evidence-based guide for clinical practice. *Eur Urol Open Sci* 39: 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.euros.2022.02.009>
- Meeks JJ, Herr HW, Bernstein M, Al-Ahmadie HA, Dalbagni G (2013) Preoperative accuracy of diagnostic evaluation of the urachal mass. *J Urol* 189: 1260–1262. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.juro.2012.10.043>
- Patel J, Villegas A (2023) Urachal adenocarcinoma: a rare primary cancer managed with FOLFOX chemotherapy. *Cureus* 15(8): e43849. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.43849>
- Quan J, Pan X, Jin L, He T, Hu J, Shi B, Peng J, Chen Z, Yang S, Mao X, Lai Y (2017) Urachal carcinoma: Report of two cases and review of the literature. *Mol Clin Oncol* 6(1): 101–104. <https://doi.org/10.3892/mco.2016.1082>
- Rajyakodi K, Gunabooshanam B, Paramasivan Sivakami MS, Sundaram S (2024) Primary urachal squamous cell carcinoma: A case report. *Cureus* 16(10): e70604. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.70604>
- Sheldon CA, Clayman RV, Gonzalez R, Williams RD, Fraley EE (1984) Malignant urachal lesions. *J Urol* 131(1): 1–8. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-5347\(17\)50167-6\[2\]](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0022-5347(17)50167-6[2])
- Siefker-Radtke A (2006) Urachal carcinoma: surgical and chemotherapeutic options. *Expert Rev Anticancer Ther* 6(12): 1715–1721. <https://doi.org/10.1586/14737140.6.12.1715>
- Szarvas T, Módos O, Niedworok C, Reis H, Szendrői A, Szász MA, Nyirády P (2016) Clinical, prognostic, and therapeutic aspects of urachal carcinoma—a comprehensive review with meta-analysis of 1,010 cases. *Urol Oncol* 34: 388–398. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.urolonc.2016.04.012>
- Wong-You-Cheong JJ, Woodward PJ, Manning MA, Sesterhenn IA (2006) Neoplasms of the urinary bladder: radiologic-pathologic correlation. *Radiographics* 26(2): 553–580. <https://doi.org/10.1148/rg.262055172>
- Yu YD, Ko YH, Kim JW, Jung SI, Kang SH, Park J, Seo HK, Kim HJ, Jeong BC, Tae-Kim H, Choi SY, Nam JK, Ku JY, Joo KJ, Jang WS, Yoon YE, Yun SJ, Hong S-H, Oh JJ (2021) The prognosis and oncological predictor of urachal carcinoma of the bladder: a large scale multicenter cohort study analyzed 203 patients with long term follow-up. *Front Oncol* 11: 1893. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fonc.2021.683190>
- Zheng H, Song W, Feng X, Zhao H (2021) Metastatic urachal carcinoma treated with several different combined regimens: A case report. *Front Oncol* 11: 662589. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fonc.2021.662589>